

MEASURES FOR THE PREVENTION OF KIDNEY DISEASES IN THE POPULATION

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Abstract. *The urinary system plays an important role in the human body, so kidney prevention must be present in life. Particular attention should be paid to preserving the health of the kidneys by persons with a predisposition, since a violation of the kidneys leads to various complications, as a result of which the development of unsafe diseases and pathological conditions is possible. That is why it is necessary to undergo medical examinations and examinations of the kidneys. The causes of kidney disease are varied. In most cases, renal pathology develops due to pathogenic microorganisms penetrating the urinary system. Toxins that have entered the body, traumatic injuries, various neoplasms, and severe allergic reactions can also provoke the manifestation of kidney disease. For the first time, signs of kidney disease in a person may appear after severe hypothermia, which entails a strong inflammatory process.*

Keywords: *prevention, kidney failure, healthy lifestyle, drinking regimen, salt.*

МЕРЫ ПО ПРОФИЛАКТИКЕ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ПОЧЕК У НАСЕЛЕНИЯ

Аннотация. *Мочевыделительная система играет важную роль в организме человека, поэтому профилактика почек должна присутствовать в жизни. Особое внимание следует уделять сохранению здоровья почек лицами с предрасположенностью, поскольку нарушение работы почек приводит к различным осложнениям, в результате которых возможно развитие опасных заболеваний и патологических состояний. Именно поэтому необходимо проходить медицинские осмотры и обследования почек. Причины заболевания почек разнообразны. В большинстве случаев патология почек развивается из-за проникновения патогенных микроорганизмов в мочевыделительную систему. Токсины, попавшие в организм, травматические повреждения, различные новообразования и тяжелые аллергические реакции также могут спровоцировать проявление заболевания почек. Впервые признаки заболевания почек у человека могут появиться после сильного переохлаждения, которое влечет за собой сильный воспалительный процесс.*

Ключевые слова: *профилактика, почечная недостаточность, здоровый образ жизни, питьевой режим, соль.*

INTRODUCTION

Sick kidneys are most often in people with overweight, an abundance of adipose tissue reduces vascular tone, excess fat presses on all organs, making it difficult for them to function. The vessels of this organ are damaged and do not work well with hypertension. The presence of diabetes provokes kidney disease, with an increased level of blood sugar, the load on all organs of the excretory system increases. Even sudden weight loss can lead to severe kidney disease, in which the kidney can move. Alcohol abuse, tobacco smoking, the use of spicy, fatty, salty and smoked foods, a sedentary lifestyle all provoke the pathology of the urinary system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Personal or individual prevention of kidney disease includes several tasks:

- maintaining kidney health in childhood and adolescence;
- protection from occupational hazards (for example, strong drafts or chemical agents);
- fight against bad habits (smoking, alcohol).

RESULTS

Let's look at each of these tasks separately. In childhood, it is necessary to monitor the work of the child's kidneys. This is especially true for girls - expectant mothers. They often have urinary tract infections caused by hypothermia and poor personal hygiene. As a result, pyelonephritis often develops. Indiscriminate sexual activity also leads to infection. Chastity, being a high moral value, protects not only the purity of the personality of a young person, but also his priceless health. It is necessary to avoid hypothermia of the kidneys at any age, but especially in childhood. Sitting on cold stones, sand, swimming in cold water are contraindicated. If the child is cold during a walk, it should be warmed in a warm bath or shower and drink hot tea. Especially strong direct drafts should be avoided - when windows or doors located opposite each other are open. You need to ventilate the apartment correctly: open the window for 15-20 minutes in one room, then close it and open it in another. If the child is sick, make sure that he is covered in bed with a blanket. Prevention is primary and secondary. Primary prevention is a complex of social, medical, hygienic and educational measures, the purpose of which is to eliminate the cause of the onset and development of kidney diseases, as well as to increase the body's resistance to the effects of harmful environmental factors (natural, industrial and domestic). Thus, primary prevention is designed to protect unimpaired health.

Secondary prevention is aimed at early detection of kidney disease, prevention of recurrence of the disease, its further progression and development. Careful attention to one's health, regular visits to medical examinations at the workplace, and, if necessary, a visit to a nephrologist are important. If a kidney disease is detected, it is necessary to become a dispensary at a nephrology center or a doctor specializing in the treatment of kidney diseases. Symptoms of kidney disease are well known: cloudy urine, change in quantity and color, pain in the lumbar region, swelling of the face, bags under the eyes, swelling of the stomach and legs, increased body temperature and blood pressure, persistent thirst and dryness in the mouth, loss appetite, general weakness, because with kidney disease, intoxication of the whole organism occurs. The kidneys that have undergone pathological changes do not remove calcium from the body well: calcium accumulates in the blood, settles on the walls of blood vessels and narrows them, this provokes the development of malfunctions of the cardiovascular system, which can lead to the development of a heart attack. In order to exclude severe complications of kidney disease, it is necessary to consult a urologist in a timely manner. Prevention of diseases of the kidneys and urinary tract implies a healthy lifestyle, physical activity, hygiene, rational nutrition. The role of rational nutrition in the prevention of kidney disease is quite large. The use of certain foods can not only aggravate the course of the disease, but also become an additional provoking factor. Reduce the amount of protein foods, cheese, chocolate, cottage cheese. Inflammatory processes, in particular, pyelonephritis of the kidneys, require a special diet for prevention. From the menu you need to exclude: spicy; salty; fatty; fried; spicy. You should also refrain from coffee and strongly brewed black tea. For the prevention of kidneys are useful: rose hips, cranberries, watermelons, fresh herbs, cucumbers, fish, cranberries, pumpkin.

DISCUSSION

A healthy adult is recommended to drink 1.5 to 2 liters of water per day. In conditions of accelerated loss of fluid from the body, the norm increases. You need to drink more during the heat, with active physical activity, dyspeptic disorders, high temperature. With the consumption of a sufficient amount of liquid, the normal activity of enzymes is possible, cleansing the body of microbes and toxins. Regular exercise and daily physical activity maintains normal blood pressure and controls blood sugar. Such actions reduce the risk of diabetes and hypertension and thus reduce the likelihood of chronic kidney disease. Eat a healthy diet full of fresh fruits and vegetables. Reduce the proportion of refined foods, sugar, fatty meats in the diet. Reducing salt intake after age 40 will help prevent high blood pressure and stone formation. Maintain your weight through a healthy diet and proper physical activity. It may help prevent diabetes, heart disease, and other conditions associated with chronic kidney disease. Smoking can lead to atherosclerosis, which reduces blood flow to the kidneys. Thus, it reduces their ability to function. Do not overuse over-the-counter pain relievers. Medicines such as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs such as analgin, indomethacin, or ibuprofen cause kidney damage and kidney failure if taken regularly. See your doctor to find a way to control your pain without putting your kidneys in danger. Drinking enough fluids (about 3 liters a day) dilutes the urine, which helps to remove all toxic waste from the body and prevent kidney stones (unless contraindicated).

Kidney diseases are often silent diseases and do not show any symptoms until the last stage of the disease is reached. The most powerful and effective, but, unfortunately, underused method of early diagnosis and prevention of kidney disease is their regular check-up (screening, clinical examination). Annual screening is mandatory for those at high risk of developing the disease, especially those with diabetes, high blood pressure, obesity, or a family history of kidney disease. If you love your kidneys (and most importantly yourself), get regular kidney checkups after age 40. A simple method for early detection of kidney disease is the annual measurement of blood pressure, urine tests and checking the level of creatinine in the blood. Be vigilant and watch for symptoms of kidney disease. Common symptoms of kidney disease are swelling of the face and legs, loss of appetite, nausea, vomiting, paleness, weakness, frequent urination, blood in the urine, or protein in the urine. In the presence of such complaints, it is recommended to immediately consult a doctor and take tests. For every patient with diabetes, precautions are of particular importance because diabetes is the leading cause of chronic kidney disease (CKD) and kidney failure worldwide. About 45% of new cases of end-stage renal failure are caused by diabetic nephropathy. For early diagnosis of kidney damage in diabetes, there is a simple and effective way to measure blood pressure for three months and urinalysis to check it for the presence of protein (macroalbuminuria). The best test for early diagnosis of diabetic nephropathy is a urine test for microalbuminuria, which should be performed every year. Measure blood creatinine and glomerular filtration rate to assess kidney function at least once a year. High blood pressure, the presence of protein in the urine, edema, frequent decreases in blood sugar, decreased insulin requirements and the appearance of diabetic eye damage (diabetic retinopathy) are important signs of kidney involvement in diabetes mellitus. Beware of these dangerous signals and consult a doctor. To prevent diabetic nephropathy in all patients with diabetes mellitus, the course of the disease should be carefully monitored: maintain blood pressure less than 130/80 mmHg (ACE inhibitors or ARBs are preferred antihypertensive drugs), reduce the amount of protein in the diet and control the level of lipids by biochemical blood

analysis. Early diagnosis and subsequent dietary restrictions, regular monitoring and proper treatment will slow down its development and allow postponing the need for dialysis or kidney transplantation.

Round-the-clock monitoring of high blood pressure is the most effective measure to prevent the progression of chronic kidney disease. It is strongly recommended to maintain blood pressure at 130/80 mmHg or even lower. The best way to control your blood pressure is to measure it at home and keep a schedule, which will help the doctor choose the right therapy.

In patients with CKD, factors such as arterial hypotension, dehydration, urinary tract obstruction, infections, sepsis, nephrotoxic drugs, etc. should be identified and taken into account. Treatment of these diseases and conditions leads to improved kidney function even with CKD. Urinary tract infection (UTI) should be assumed when a child has fever of unknown origin, frequent urination, soreness and burning when urinating, poor appetite or insufficient weight gain. It is important to remember that a UTI with a high temperature carries a risk of kidney damage, especially if the disease was detected late, or when the treatment was performed late or was absent altogether. Such injuries include kidney scars, weak kidney growth, high blood pressure, and kidney failure in later life. For this reason, children with urinary tract infection need not only early diagnosis and timely treatment, but also to identify the main predisposing abnormalities and risk factors. Vesicoureteral reflux (PMR) is the most common predisposing cause - currently it causes about 50% of cases of urinary tract infections in childhood. All children with UTI should be closely monitored.

CONCLUSIONS

In a broad sense, prevention is a system of state, social, medical and hygienic measures aimed at preventing diseases and maintaining a high level of health. If the main direction in the health care system is recognized as preventive, then this is expressed in the creation of a system of socio-economic and medical measures to eliminate the causes of diseases and the formation of favorable living conditions. If the state for any reason is unable to provide full-fledged financing of the relevant programs, most of the responsibility for taking preventive measures falls on the shoulders of the citizens themselves.

REFERENCES

1. Agranovich, N. V. (2013). The Rationale and Effectiveness of Precaution and Treatment of Chronic Kidney Diseases patients in Out-patient Conditions.
2. Zemchenkov, A. Yu., & Konakova, I. N. (2015). The chronic kidney disease progression rates according to St.-Petersburg CKD register. *Nephrology and Dialysis*.
3. Couser, W. G., Remuzzi, G., Mendis, S., & Tonelli, M. (2011). The contribution of chronic kidney disease to the global burden of major noncommunicable diseases.
4. Lin, B., Shao, L., Luo, Q., Ou-yang, L., Zhou, F., Du, B., ... & Chen, J. (2014). Prevalence of chronic kidney disease and its association with metabolic diseases.
5. Turdalievich T. A., Gulyam Y. Morphological features of pedolytical soils in Central Ferghana //European science review. – 2016. – №. 5-6. – C. 14-15.
6. Valijanovich M. O. et al. Biogeochemistry Properties of Calcisols and Capparis Spinosa L //Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology. – 2021. – C. 3227-3235.
7. Turdaliev, A., Yuldashev, G., Askarov, K., & Abakumov, E. (2021). Chemical and biogeochemical features of desert soils of the central Fergana. *Agriculture*, 67(1), 16-28.

8. Броварский, В. Д., Турдалиев, А. Т., & Мирзахмедова, Г. И. (2020). Воздействие температуры окружающей среды на пчел и растения. Научное обозрение. Биологические науки, (3), 43-48.